
Impacts of On-going and Completed Self-Help Projects on the Residents of Kaiama Local Government Area, Kwara State, Nigeria

Abdulsalaam Abdulhakeem Madaki

Department of Geography and Planning Science, Faculty of the Social Sciences, Ekiti State University, Ado Ekiti, Nigeria

E-Mail: hakeemsalaam29@gmail.com

Abstract This study examined the impacts of ongoing and completed self-help projects on the residents of Kaiama Local Government Area; Kwara State, Nigeria. Data for this study were collected from primary and secondary sources. Results from this study revealed that projects needed for the development of the study area is considerably very low; especially the self-help projects. This study therefore recommended that, Community Associations should be restructured to be in the line with best practices. Their activities should be supervised and regulated by the Ministry of Commerce and Enterprise in the State. In some communities, most people are mere participants in self-help activities but do not in the actual sense play a meaningful role in initiating and controlling development projects in their own interest.

Keywords Developments, Impacts, People, Projects, Self-Help

Introduction

One of the major characteristics of the developing countries is the increasing disparity between the urban and rural areas. According to Ayeni [1] “within the facets of community development, it is increasingly understood that social infrastructure and service play a crucial role in addressing exclusion and achieving the goals of poverty reduction, gender equality and sustainable development”.

In Nigeria, there is a necessity for the development of the rural areas because the gap in economic and social development between urban and rural areas in Nigeria continues to widen leading to social crisis and dissatisfaction. Rural development is a strategy designed to improve the economic condition of a specific group of people – the rural poor. It involves extending the benefits of the development to the poorest among those who seek a livelihood in the rural area.

Government grant aided self-help as a strategy for community and rural development was given a greater prominence in the Third National Development Plan. Communities were incorporated into the framework of the national development plan. As mentioned in the plan, activities in the sector of community and rural development will take the form of self-help projects by various communities under the agencies of the local government authorities with the state government providing technical and financial support whenever such project are initiated. Such projects includes construction of village roads, markets, dispensaries, schools and other amenities directed towards the development of their various localities (Federal Republic of Nigeria).

Statement of the Problem

Rural development as a strategy is a form of state intervention aimed at improving the living standard or wellbeing of the majority of the rural dwellers and to make the rural areas more productive, to raise income and to ensure that any development is self-sustaining and involves the majority of the people. According to Mahmud

[2] rural development must be given priority on the 'Must Do List' of government at different levels if the rural communities must contribute meaningfully to the social, cultural and economic development of Nigeria.

Giving the contribution of the rural sector in the National economy, the rural sector of Nigeria is vital to the socio-economic development of the nation. According to Nyagba [3] the most important sector of the Nigerian population is the rural areas. This sector is the major source of capital formation for the country and a principal market for domestic and raw materials for industrial processes [4].

Since community development as a field study concerns the behavioral phenomenon of a group, its success depends very much on the internal structure of organization of the group undertaking the projects and the behavior of leaders within the group, value and norms of the group. This study therefore, attempts to assess the impact of community development projects in Kaiama Local Government Area of Kwara State.

Research Questions

- i. What are the problems of the various on-going and completed self-help projects on the residents of Kaiama Local Government Area?
- ii. What are the impacts of the various on-going and completed self-help projects on the residents of Kaiama Local Government Area?

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The study aimed at examining the impacts of on-going and completed self-help projects in Kaiama Local Government Area of Kwara State.

To achieve this aim, the following specific objectives are set to;

- i. examine the problems of the various on-going and completed self-help projects on the residents of Kaiama Local Government Area;
- ii. assess the impact of the various on-going and completed self-help projects on the residents of Kaiama Local Government Area;
- iii. Proffer possible solutions to the identified problems in the study area.

The Study Area

Location

The study area Kaiama Local Government Area is situated, on $9^{\circ}38' 19.08''$ north latitude, $3^{\circ} 56' 27.64''$ East longitude and 314 meters elevation above sea level. It has a land mass of 6971 km² and estimated population of 124,164 in 2006 census figure. At 2.5% annual growth rate, the population is expected to limit 167,621 by the year 2020.

Socio-economic activities

Economically, majority of the inhabitants engaged in agricultural activities and small scale industrial like blacksmithing, trading, photography, blocks making, bread industries, and shear butter processing among others. The area is socially provided with amenities like hospitals, schools, banks post office, hotels, and petrol stations.

Figure 1: Map of Nigeria showing Kwara State Source: Office of the Surveyor General, 2020

Figure 2: Map of Kwara State showing Kaiama Local Government Area Source: Office of the Surveyor General, 2020.

Figure 3: Map of Kaiama Local Government Area showing the Study Areas Source: Office of the Surveyor General, 2020

Conceptual Framework and Literature Review

Industrial Development Model

Development economists have made a strong case for rural industrialization as a pre-requisite to rural development. It is argued that locating industries in rural areas will affect the rural economies along favourable lines. However, this view appears to ignore the fact that certain industries located along theoretically expected lines in rural areas have failed to make any significant impact on the areas. A typical example is cement manufacturing, an urban-type industry, which is raw-materials oriented. This industry is often located at sites of limestone, its most important raw material, whereas much of the technical skills required are sourced from non local sources. Sometimes, only unskilled (manual) labour may be sourced from the neighborhood where the industry is sited.

Area Development Model

This model of rural development advocates a comprehensive development of unique area units, such as river basins, fertile agricultural lands or mineralized zones. Usually, emphasis is on providing improved varieties and infrastructure to a targeted area within a country. Agriculture, industry, transportation, forestry etc. are developed through a comprehensive development programme formulated and executed by appropriate authorities, often with the aid of the World Bank and other international organizations.

Methodology

Research design

This research work made use of both primary and secondary data. Primary data were obtained directly from the field, through direct observation, responses obtained from questionnaire administration and personal interviews with stakeholders in rural development planning sphere (that includes ministry of local government and chieftaincy affairs, community development association). Primary data was also sourced through photography and personal observation.

Secondary data was obtained from published works of other researchers in journals, text books, and official records, and monographs, aerial and other maps. In order to generate the required sample units for the study, Krejcie and Morgan, [5] model was adopted to determine the sample size. This is an online based tool. It requires that the necessary information be plugged in, such as population size when data required is supplied, the sample size of such is therefore generated.

Population of the study

The population of the study Area as at 2006 census figures stands at 124,167. When projected to 2020 at 2.5% growth would be 164,142 as at the time of the study.

Table 1: Population of kaiama local government

LGA	2006 Population Census	Projected Population TO2020 AT 2.5% growth rate
Kaiama	124,167	167,142

Source: Population census 2006 and Author, 2020.

This formula employed in calculating the projected population $P_e = P_n (1 + R/100)^N$

P_t = Projected population

P_n = Present Population

R = Growth Rate

N = Number of Years

R is given as 2.5%

Sample and Sampling Technique

A multi-stage sampling was employed to select respondents. The first stage was a purposive selection of all the seven sub-districts of the study area. The second stage was random sampling selection of two (2) villages from the sub-districts making a total of 14 villages. The third stage involved responses from twenty-five (25) or less respondents from each of the selected villages depending on the sizes. The total samples amounted to three

hundred and fifty (350) respondents. Aside from these, three (3) members of executives of the community development association (i.e. chairmen, secretary and treasurer) were sampled. The cumulative sampled amount to 417 respondents. Person's product moment correlation was used to test relationship between self-help projects and standard of living of members of the community, and chi-square analysis was also used to check the degree of cooperation and contribution of community members to self-help projects.

Data collected was analyzed and interpreted using descriptive and inferential statistic assisted with the use of Package for Social Sciences SPSS version (23).

Research Instruments

A research instrument is a tool use to obtain, measure, and analyse data. For the purpose of this work, two types of instruments were used to collect data for the study. (i) survey and direct interview with respondents, (ii) structured questionnaire administration. Data were collected directly by the researcher through observation of events on the field and discussion with respondents and data elicited through questionnaires.

Validity of Research Instrument

The research instruments adopted for this study were subjected to vetting, scrutiny and screening by the researcher's supervisor, and other experts in the Department of Geography and Planning Science, Ekiti State University, Ado Ekiti. Irrelevant aspect/items were expunged to refine the instruments to reflect the appropriateness of measures that can collect relevant data.

Methods of Data Collection

The instruments for the study were administered by the researcher with the help of three (3) trained assistants. The permission of the village heads were sought and obtained questionnaires was thereafter given out to respondents to elicit data relevant to the study. Also, data were collected through personal discussions between the researcher and identified groups like the old students association, social club members etc., and community development departments and agencies. Personal observation was also used to collect data from the field.

Methods of Data Analysis

The data obtained for the study were analyzed using descriptive statistics which include frequency counts, percentage, mean and standard deviation while the inferential statistics used are chi-squared and Pearson Product Moment correlation (PPMC) Hypothesis 1 Was tested using the chi-squared. It analysed the degree of cooperation and contribution of community members to self-help projects, while hypothesis 2 tested the relationship between self-help projects and standard of living of members of the community using PPMC. All hypothesis formulated were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

The research work covers the entire Kaiama Local Government Area which is one of the sixteen local government areas of Kwara state. It comprises of Kaiama district and seven sub-districts, which include Adena, Gwaria, Bani, Kemanji, Kukugi, Gwanabe and Kaiama. Each of this sub districts comprises of small towns and villages.

Results and Discussions

Table 1: Social Impact of Self-help Projects on the Community

Item	Frequency	Percentage
Reduction of out migration	201	48.2
Improved healthcare	141	33.8
Viewing centre	3	0.7
Reduction in crime	15	3.6
Town hall/socialization	57	13.7
Total	417	100.0

Field Survey, 2020

Results presented in table 10, on the social impact of self-help projects on the community revealed that, 201 representing 48.2% of the respondents said it has helped in the reduction of out migration, 33.8% of the respondents said it has helped in the improvement of healthcare facilities, 3 representing 0.7% of the respondents opined that it has increased viewing centres in the communities, 15 representing 3.6% of the respondents said it has helped in the reduction of crime while 57 representing 13.7% of the respondents noted that it has increased town hall/events in the communities.

From the results obtained, it can be deduced that the major social impact on self-help community based projects include reduction in out migration (emigration), and improvement in healthcare facilities. It also has some slight impact on the increase in social events that takes place in the communities.

Table 2: Economic Impacts of Self-help Projects on the Community

Item	Frequency	Percentage
Employment	311	74.6
Agricultural extension programme	83	19.9
Improved communication	5	1.2
Loan scheme	18	4.3
Total	417	100.0

Field Survey, 2020

Results presented on table 11, on the economic impact of self-help projects on the communities showed that 311 representing 74.6% of the respondents noted that it has helped in the employment of people in the agricultural sector in the community. Community members have benefited through semi-skilled and skilled labours during projects implementation. 83 representing 19.9% of the respondents said it has contributed in the area of agricultural extension programme, 5 representing 1.2% of the respondents said it has led to improved communication while 18 representing 4.3 said it had improved loan scheme.

From the result presented, it can be deduced that the major economic impact of self-help projects in the communities was the provision of jobs and agricultural extension programmes.

Table 3: Physical Impacts of Self-help Projects on the Community

Item	Frequency	Percentage
Feeder road	75	17.9
Borehole projects	115	27.6
Vocation centre	155	37.2
Culvert/bridges	72	17.3
Total	417	100.0

Field Survey, 2020

Result presented on table 12, the physical impacts of self-help projects on the community showed that 75 representing 17.9% of the respondents were of the opinion that self-help projects has contributed to feeder roads in the communities, 115 representing 27.6% of the respondents said it has contributed in the provision of borehole projects in the communities, 155 representing 37.2% of the respondents said it has contributed in the provision of vocation centres in the communities while 72 representing 17.3% said it has contributed to the number of culverts and bridges in the communities.

The major physical impact of self-help projects to the communities was construction of boreholes for water supply in all the communities and vocation centres for skills acquisition and human capital development. There was also minor contributions to feeder roads, culverts/bridges etc.

Table 4: Response on if opportunities are given to rural people to initiate community projects

Item	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	94	22.4
No	323	77.5
Total	417	100.0

Field Survey, 2020

Results presented on table 13, the problems associated with the provision of infrastructural facilities in Kaiama Local Government area showed that 94 representing 22.4% of the respondents agreed that rural people should

be allowed to initiate community projects while 323 representing 77.5% of the respondents disagreed. In essence, it can be inferred that the Government did not usually allow community associations to initiate community based project on their own terms. This therefore, affected the level of self-help projects that they can be initiated or builds for the community.

Recommendations

Sequel to the summary of findings, the following recommendations was put forward towards community development participation in future development programme in the area.

Community associations should be restructured to be in the line with best practices. Their activities should be supervised and regulated by the Ministry of Commerce and Enterprise. This is to ensure proper accountability for all funds meant for community projects, and promote stability in the running of the association.

Financing community projects has always been an up-hill task. It is thus recommended that revolving loans and agricultural inputs such as fertilizers, improved seedlings, chemicals etc. should be readily available to increase the capacity of the inhabitants. Also, agricultural extension programme will go a long way in bringing the farmers in-tune with global practices. This will invaluable improve the yields and ultimately their capacity to contribute to community development activities.

Federal, state, local government and non-governmental organization should improve the state of infrastructures in the community. Feeder roads should be upgraded to ensure ease of access to farmlands while the existing and on-going health and educational facilities should be improved upon, thereby improving the quality of lives of the community and ultimately reduced the prevalent of educational and medical tourism. There should be decentralization of leadership in all activities relating to ownership and control of infrastructure at the community level.

Finally, projects implementation should be prioritized to avoid abandonment of projects and wasteful duplication of resources.

Conclusion

On the basis of the foregoing discussions, a conclusion could be reached that self-help is a relevant strategy for rural development in Nigeria like the cooperative movement, the self-help movement in many parts of Nigeria rest on the rich tradition of people. We found also that local communities in Kaiama Kwara state and other states in Nigeria have been undertaking self-help project from time immemorial. But the latest development in self-help activities is the partnership which the government now formed with the people.

It has been established that there is a relationship between times related events and the motive force that sustained self-help development activities in Kaiama, Kwara State. These motive forces have been idealized to relate to (a) the instinct of self and cooperate survival and (b) the societal felt need. It is these two principles, which are known to vary spatially and temporarily, that govern the inner dynamics of self-help activities and thus dictates the observed spatial variations in the attainment of economic well-being.

In the self-help strategy, intrinsic value is accorded to participation. This is reflected in the opinions of development *i.e.* to benefit the people; they must participate in planning and implementing their development plans. In some communities, most people are mere participants in self-help activities but do not in the actual sense play a meaningful role in initiating and controlling development projects in their own interest. Community elites do not often perceive their interest as identical with those of the community as a whole though sometimes they contribute more than their share both in terms of financial contributions and individual efforts.

Furthermore, people's participation cannot be said to have increased when some development projects were imposed on them by outsiders who may be ignorant of the real needs of the communities. In most cases, particularly where technical assistance or matching grants are made available to the self-help groups, bureaucratic control over decision making becomes a prominent feature of self-help activities.

Lastly, the success of self-help efforts in Nigeria is sometimes hindered by the corrupt attitude of both development official and the community elite. It is a common feature to hear various situations, where the rural elite spearhead self-help projects as an avenue for self-enrichment and political gains. Community development

officials in like manner, fall victim to the same offence by receiving grafts to render services which are supposed to be given free of charge.

References

- [1]. Ayeni, A. J. (2017). Teachers' classroom management and quality assurance of students' learning outcome in secondary schools in Ondo State, Nigeria. *Journal of Social and Administrative Sciences*, 4(2), 166-180.
- [2]. Mahmud, R. (2019). Mixed implications of private supplementary tutoring for students' learning: Urban and rural disparities in Bangladesh. *International Journal of Comparative Education and Development*, 21 (1), 61-75.
- [3]. Nyagba, S. (2009) "Review of Nigeria's Rural Development Policy for sustainable Development" paper presented at Business Round Table at Abuja, 9–11 July.
- [4]. Ugwuanyi, B. I., & Chukwuemeka, E. E. (2013). The obstacles to effective policy implementation by the public bureaucracy in developing nations: the case of Nigeria. *Kuwait Chapter of Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review*, 33(856), 1-10.
- [5]. Krejcie, R. V., & Morgan, D. W. (1970). Determining sample size for research activities. *Educational and psychological measurement*, 30(3), 607-610.

